

Effectiveness of Multisensory Teaching Approach for Children with Intellectual Disabilities

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ABSTRACT: A multisensory teaching approach helps enhance the skills of children with intellectual & developmental disabilities (IDDs). This study explores the effectiveness of a multisensory teaching approach for students with intellectual disabilities. This study was qualitative and phenomenological. A sample of 20 participants, including males and females, was selected by using a purposive sampling technique. Researchers used a semi-structured interview to collect data. Validity of the instrument was confirmed through expert opinion (n=02), and reliability was examined through an extensive literature review. After data collection, interviews with participants were transcribed, and the open coding technique was applied. The process of data analysis was performed manually by generating codes and then through qualitative data analysis software NVivo version 15. Five major themes emerged from the data analysis process, i.e., prevailing endeavors, kinesthetic approaches, challenges in multisensory teaching approaches, teaching strategies, and required resources. The findings revealed that teachers consider the multisensory approach highly effective for their students' needs, but teachers require professional training and better resources to implement it fully.

Key words: Multisensory Teaching, Intellectual Disability, Children, Special Education.

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1. Introduction

Using a multisensory approach helps students with intellectual disabilities in their learning. Some children learn best when they see something, some learn best when they

hear it, and many learn best when they move or touch it (Maryanti, 2021; Soon et al., 2025). Using sensory-based stimulation is one way to promote interaction (Yuile et al., 2021; Hettiarachchi et al., 2022).

Children with intellectual disabilities benefit greatly from the use of multisensory instruction. Because it employs multiple senses simultaneously, this approach is beneficial (Azeri, 2025). A multi-sensory technique combines visual and auditory strategies at the same time. For many learning activities, kinesthetic and/or tactile strategies are also employed (Mohamed, 2021; Saha & Adhisari, 2023). The multisensory method provides flexibility in learning. (Nurjanah et al., 2024).

Multisensory activities improve education and make learning more pleasurable. Flashcards, photographs, tablet LCDs, and other visual aids are employed in multisensory exercises. Stories are told, audio is played, speaking toys are employed, and sounds are repeated for auditory learners. Using textured materials, tracing letters with fingers, building blocks, feeling actual objects with the hands, and creating something with beads are all ways to get a tactile sensation. Kinesthetic activities include bodily movement, such as creating an alphabet shape or engaging in physical activities like running, jumping, and bouncing. It talks about the ways that visual aids, multimodal methods, and game-based learning strategies have been shown to enhance communication, motor skills, and comprehension (Jumanova, 2025; Koifman, 2025).

Problem Statement

Children with intellectual disabilities experience difficulty in learning. Therefore, the problem statement is to explore the effectiveness **of multi-sensory teaching for children with intellectual disabilities.**

Objectives of the Research

- Find out existing practices of the multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities in schools.
- Identify challenges faced by teachers in administering a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities.
- Highlight strategies implemented by teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with ID.
- Explore resources required for teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with ID.

Research Questions

1. What are the existing practices of the multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities in schools?
2. What are the challenges faced by teachers in administering a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?
3. What strategies are implemented by teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?
4. What resources are required for teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?

Limitations & De-limitations of Study

1. The study was limited to the province of Punjab only.
2. Only the teachers of children with intellectual disabilities were included in the sample of the study.
3. Researchers developed a semi-structured interview due to the unavailability of a standardized questionnaire.
4. The researchers selected a qualitative approach for this study to get in-depth insight into the phenomenon.

2. Literature Review

Children with intellectual disabilities frequently exhibit challenging behaviors, which can negatively impact their opportunities and quality of life (Lye et al., 2025). According to the DSM-5, intellectual disability is characterized by substantial impairments in both intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior, as demonstrated by conceptual, social, and practical adaptive skills in people five years of age or older (Rodan et al., 2025; Sousa, 2024). Students gained the ability to classify exemplars according to audio-visual spatial cues, auditory-only cues (spatially specified soundscape), or visual-only cues (geometric shape) (O'Dowd et al., 2025; Maqsood et al., 2025). Any teaching tool that uses the five senses, seeing, hearing, feeling, smelling, and so forth, is considered a teaching aid, not just books, whiteboards, and photographs (Kassim & Nordin, 2024; Gao, 2025). A key component of the multisensory method, which has a remarkable impact on raising primary school students' reading proficiency, is the incorporation of multisensory elements into everyday instruction (Adiningtyas, 2025; Kachur, 2025). Traditional play is often used to help children with intellectual disabilities (ID) improve motor skills. However, these activities may lack structured sensory input (Intani et al., 2025). In light of this, the multisensory approach works to help children with minor intellectual disabilities who struggle in this area learn certain language skills (Samira et al., 2025; Lee & Kim, 2025). Teaching is greatly aided by the use of a multimodal method (Liang Soon et al., 2025). Gaining an understanding of classification levels guarantees that multisensory approaches are successfully customized, resulting in more significant educational opportunities (Yusuf et al., 2025). Seidl et al. (2024) found two ways in which rich multimodal experiences could help students learn words.

3. Research Methodology

Research Design

The study used a qualitative research design with a phenomenological type of study.

Population of the Study

The population of this study includes teachers teaching children with intellectual disabilities and are working in public and private level educational schools in Punjab.

Sample of the Study

The sample for the study included 20 teachers teaching children with intellectual disabilities (N=20). Both males (N=5) and females (N=15) participants were included in the sample. Samples were collected from different cities of Punjab, including Lahore, Qasoor, Renala Khurd, Mandi Bahauddin, Dera Ghazi Khan, Bahawalpur, Kot Addu, Gojra, Rahim

Yar Khan, Pattoki, Ahmadpur East, Kot Chutta, Sargodha, and Chaubara. The age range of the sample was between 28 and 46 years. The sample detail has been given below in the table 1:

Table 1: Sample Details as per their Demographics

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Male	5	25%
Female	15	75%
Less than 10 years exp	9	45%
More than 10 years exp	11	55%
Jr. special education teachers	14	70%
Senior special education teachers	6	30%
MA/BS/B.Ed Hons	8	40%
MS/M.Phil	6	30%
Ph.D	6	30%
25-30 Yrs age	3	15%
31-35 Yrs age	5	25%
36-40 Yrs age	7	35%
Above 40 Yrs of age	5	25%

Sampling Technique

In this study, the purposive sampling technique was used for data collection.

Instrument for data collection

A self-developed semi-structured interview was used as an instrument for this study. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section I was created to collect demographic information. Section II was composed of the core interview questions. The instrument consisted of nine open-ended questions with a few probing questions, which allowed participants to express their experiences in their own words.

Validity & Reliability of Instrument

The validity of the instrument was assured by the expert opinion (N=02). The reliability of the instrument was ensured through an extensive literature review.

Data collection

Before starting the data collection process, permission was obtained from the teachers to conduct online interviews. Every participant was clearly informed about the purpose of the study and the use of their data. The researcher had to read and interpret the questions in a familiar language to the respondent and conduct the interviews. Probing questions were also asked according to the flow of the discussion and the need to gain deeper insight into the teachers' lived experiences. All responses were audio-recorded with the teachers' permission.

Data Analysis

First of all, all the interviews were transcribed. After transcription, the open coding technique was administered by the researchers, and the categories emerged from the data. These categories were supported by sub-themes and the chunks from the original data. Based on the categories, major themes emerged. After manual data analysis, this data was further analyzed through qualitative data analysis software NVivo version 15. The software helped to organize the large amount of data and was used to generate a word tree and systematic tables as part of the completion of the data analysis. This software analysis ensured that the themes were strong, clear, and data-based. In the final stage, every theme was explained in detail in paragraph form.

Ethical Consideration for This Study

The researchers followed all the ethical considerations during this research strictly. Before commencing the study, it was decided by the researchers to comply with all research ethics properly. Participants were also informed earlier about the time of the interviews and the confidentiality of their responses.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Thematic Analysis

Main Hierarchy

The qualitative data analysis of the semi-structured interview with the teachers of children with intellectual disabilities was conducted using software NVivo – 15. Major themes and sub-themes are presented in the above word chart.

Research Question 1: What are the existing practices of the multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities in schools?

Prevailing Endeavors	
Resource scarcity	Effective Practices
Need Centered Approach	Demonstration

Theme 1: **Prevailing Endeavors**

This theme depicts the existing practices of the teachers for the implementation of the multisensory teaching approach in special education schools for children with intellectual disabilities. The theme has emerged from the categories of effective practices, demonstration, need-centered approach, resource scarcity, and real-life experience. Child profiles play a crucial role in assisting educators in selecting appropriate teaching strategies and media. This curriculum uses drill and multisensory methods, with the use of flashcards, posters, and songs (Khoshimov, 2023).

Category 1: **Effective practices**

This category reveals participants' responses about effective practices regarding the use of a multisensory approach for children with intellectual disabilities. Participants of the study expressed that a multisensory approach is an effective way of working with children. One participant narrated that:

"I believe that the multisensory approach is highly effective for enhancing children's learning.

Category 2: **Demonstration**

This category depicts participants' responses about the use of a multisensory teaching approach in front of children with ID. Participants shared that when they perform an activity first in front of children, the children watch the steps and try to follow them. One participant narrated that:

"I believe that when we demonstrate something to them using their senses, they understand better."

Category 3: **Need Centered Approach**

This category shows the participants' responses about the use of teaching techniques according to the children's needs. Most participants said that understanding each child's learning requirements is very important. One participant shared that:

"These children have different sensory needs, and this teaching approach fulfills them."

Category 4: **Resources Scarcity**

This category reflects participants' views about the lack of resources for teaching children with intellectual disabilities. Most participants mentioned that not having enough teaching materials or tools makes it difficult to use a multisensory approach effectively. One participant explained:

"When we use the multisensory approach, managing the class becomes difficult because of this approach."

Kinesthetic Approaches	
Visualized Activities	Auditory Activities
Hands On Experience	

Theme 2: **Kinesthetic Approaches**

This theme reflects the teachers' views on the types of multisensory activities that children with intellectual disabilities respond to most positively in special education classrooms. The theme has emerged from the categories of visualized activities, auditory activities, and hands-on experiences. When it comes to touch, sound, or food texture, children with Sensory Processing Disorder (SPD) frequently overreact. However, with the right therapy, children's sensory issues can be lessened and even treated (Mohsen & Hegazy, 2021).

Category 1: **Visualized Activities**

This category depicts participants' views in which participants shared that these children pay more attention and stay interested when pictures, flashcards, videos, or real objects are used in teaching. It also makes learning more meaningful and enjoyable for the children. One of the participants said that:

"In my experience, visual activities get the best response from our students."

Category 2: **Auditory Activities**

This category depicts participants' responses in which participants said many students learn better when they listen to songs, rhymes, or spoken words during class. When teachers talk again and again about a concept, or use music and stories, children start paying more

attention and try to respond. One of the participants narrated that: "Most of the children are music lovers; they like things related to sound."

Category 3: Hands-On Experiences

This category shows that children with intellectual disabilities learn better when they use their hands and touch different things during activities. Participants expressed that when children hold objects, feel different materials, or do tasks like pasting and sorting, they stay more interested. These activities help them understand lessons easily because they learn by doing. According to one participant:

"Most of the time, my class students respond to tactile activities. They learn and enjoy the most from this activity."

Research Question 2: What are the challenges faced by teachers in administering a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?

Challenges In Multisensory Teaching Approach	
Multitasking	High Student - Teacher Ratio
Insufficient Teacher Training	Diverse Sensory Needs

Theme 3: **Challenges in Multisensory Teaching Approach**

This theme highlights the challenges teachers face while implementing a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities. The participants expressed various difficulties that influence how effectively they can use this approach in their classrooms. These challenges emerged from the categories of multitasking, high student-teacher ratio, diverse sensory needs, and insufficient teacher training. Pakistan is one of the many industrialized and developing countries that do not set aside a sufficient amount of money to address the needs of children with disabilities (Kim & Park, 2022).

Category 1: **Multitasking**

This category displays the participants' responses about the challenges that teachers experience while applying a multisensory teaching approach in their classes. The participants of the study highlighted that multitasking is the biggest challenge for them while working on a multisensory teaching approach. They are bound to perform a few other tasks with their teaching job in schools, which increases the work pressure on them. One of the participants added that.

"If I talk specifically about government institutions, the biggest challenge we face is the extra work."

Category 2: **High Student-Teacher Ratio**

This category reflects the challenges teachers face due to the high number of students and limited staff. Participants reported that managing a large class with children of different ages, abilities, and sensory needs is very difficult. One participant revealed that

"The most basic thing is manpower; we need to have enough manpower to manage all these things. The student-teacher ratio is very high."

Category 3: **Diverse Sensory Needs**

This category shows that children have different ways of learning through their senses. Some like to see, some like to hear, and some learn by touching or moving. Teachers noticed that one method does not work for all. They change their activities and materials to fit each child's needs. Paying attention to these differences makes learning easier and more meaningful for the students. As stated by one participant, that

"The children with intellectual disabilities have chronological age and mental age that are different."

Category 4: **Insufficient Teacher Training**

This category reveals the participants' responses about the challenges they face due to insufficient teacher training in applying the multisensory teaching approach. Many of them feel uncertain about how to plan activities or use the materials effectively for children with different abilities. As one participant expressed that

"Internally, the biggest challenge is the teacher's mindset and dedication. If a teacher is not mentally prepared, determined, and passionate about working with these children, then no method will be successful."

Research Question 3: What are the strategies implemented by teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?

Theme 4: **Teaching Strategies**

This theme depicts the strategies used by teachers to adapt multisensory teaching methods according to the individual needs, interests, and learning styles of children with intellectual disabilities. The theme has emerged from the categories of adaptation, using instructional materials, influencing music patterns, and implementing assistive technology. Children's engagement and memory retention are improved by a multimodal approach, technology integration, and the active participation of parents and instructors (Faqihuddin et al., 2024).

Category 1: **Adaptation**

This category reveals participants' responses in which they narrated that they use simple objects, real-life materials, and easy tasks so that children can learn without confusion. One of the participants described that.

"Yes, we have to adapt our multisensory teaching methods according to the needs of each child. For example, sometimes we may have blocks as a material. We can teach those blocks for counting, and then we also teach the children shapes with the same blocks."

Category 2: **Using Instructional Material**

This category highlights the use of flashcards and charts in classrooms. The participants of the study said that these helped children see and understand concepts.

Repeating pictures and flashcards often helps children recognize and remember objects. One of the participants said that.

We always use flashcards to teach children. We also make charts to support their learning, and when needed, we draw the same shapes or objects on the whiteboard to help the children understand better.”

Category 3: Influencing Music Patterns

This category highlights participants’ regarding the use of music in different class times. Many participants explained that rhythmic sounds and songs help children become more attentive, learn words through audio, and gain the concepts more easily. Music not only brings joy but also helps in language development, emotional regulation, and social interaction during group activities. One participant explained that:

“I play Surah Rahman softly, and during activity time, if we are doing a group session or music time, I play rhymes or songs to engage the children.

Category 4: Implementing Assistive Technology

This category identifies the participants’ responses about the use of assistive technology as a tool of multisensory teaching in class. The participants of the study responded that things like LED, mobile, laptop, and small speakers help them play rhymes, stories, and different sounds for the children. According to teachers, when sound and pictures come together, children show more interest and understand better. One of the participants said that.

“I use that Bluetooth mic and attach a small speaker to it. I use LED more for auditory material. Because when things are moving with motion, both audio and video, children understand and like them well.”

Research Question 4: What are the resources required for teachers in using a multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities?

Required Resources	
Technological and Digital Resources	Sensory and Motor Resources
Teaching -Learning Materials	Infrastructural and Human Support

Theme 5: **Required Resources**

This theme represents teachers' views about the essential resources required for implementing the multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities. The theme has emerged from the categories of technological and digital resources, teaching-learning materials, sensory and motor resources, and infrastructural and human support. To increase learning effectiveness, additional work was still required, especially in the areas of encouraging more active interactions, using a variety of learning media, and implementing more tangible and participatory teaching strategies (Buta et al., 2025)

Category 1: **Technological and Digital Resources**

This category identifies the participants' responses in which participants shared that technological and digital resources are very important for their classes. The participants of the study shared that tools like LED screens, multimedia projectors, tablets, and classroom computers play an essential role in increasing IDD children's focus and participation, and these tools further increase the children's attention. Participants of the study further endorsed that resources make lessons more interactive and help teachers give visual and auditory input more effectively. One of the participants expressed that.

"I believe an LED screen should be available in every classroom for ID children."

Category 2: **Teaching-Learning Materials**

This category depicts the importance of teaching and learning materials that help teachers apply the multisensory approach successfully in classrooms for children with intellectual disabilities. Teachers point out that having suitable materials such as flashcards, charts, tactile objects, sensory boards, puzzles, and AV aids makes it easier for children to gain an understanding through touch, sight, and sound. One of the participants mentioned that.

"These include tools for: Fine motor activities, like peg boards, threading kits, and small puzzles. Gross motor activities, like gym balls, soft mats, and large foam blocks."

Category 3: **Sensory and Motor Resources**

This category highlights the participants' responses about the required resources for them to work on multisensory teaching for children with intellectual disabilities. The participants of the study endorsed the importance of sensory and motor resources in multisensory teaching for children with intellectual disabilities. The participants of the study further shared that using materials that involve touch, movement, and physical activity helps children in developing fine and gross motor skills, improving coordination, and staying more focused."

Category 4: **Infrastructural and Human Support**

This category contains the participants' responses about the importance of infrastructural and human resources in using the multisensory teaching approach for children with intellectual disabilities. The participants of the study responded that having sufficient classroom space, sensory rooms, and trained support staff, such as occupational therapists, psychologists, and helpers, is essential for effective teaching."

Findings:

1. Existing Practices

This study found that Teachers described multisensory teaching as an effective, regularly used approach for children with intellectual disabilities. They explain that children gain a better understanding when visual, auditory, tactile, and movement-based activities are combined.

2. Kinaesthetic Approaches

The findings illustrated that children reacted most to the activities that matched their interests, pursuits, and involved multiple senses. Teachers describe that visual activities, such as colourful flashcards, videos, and real-life demonstrations, catch the children's attention and help them learn better from these activities. Tactile activities like touching different textures, playing with blocks, and handling objects worked very well for the children with intellectual disabilities. Kinesthetic activities like movement, dancing, exercising, and jumping also helped and assisted the children to stay engaged, occupied, focused, and understand better.

3. Challenges for Teachers

The findings revealed that Teachers faced several challenges when using multisensory teaching for children with intellectual disabilities. The biggest problem was the lack of materials and resources, like sensory tools, visual aids, or learning objects, which made it difficult to teach effectively. Large class sizes made it challenging to give each child individual attention, especially since every child had different abilities and sensory preferences. Teachers also experience children's behavioral issues. Limited training of teachers, lack of support from staff, school administrators, and little cooperation from parents contributed to these difficulties.

4. Strategies Implemented by Teachers

The findings of this study showed that teachers adjusted or adapted their teaching in different ways to match each child's sensory needs. They watched and observed their students closely to see what they liked, what attracted them, and what they were good at, and how they learned best, whether by seeing, hearing, touching, or moving. They changed and adapted activities according to the child's needs, such as using blocks or playdough for hands-on learning, songs or rhymes for listening, and movement games for those who learned by moving. Teachers made tasks simpler and easier for the children with intellectual disabilities and broke them into small steps. Teachers also changed and adapted the classroom setup whenever required. Sometimes, they taught the children through modelling, one-to-one, or in small groups, especially those who have short attention spans, focus difficulties, or specific sensory needs.

5. Resource Requirements

The findings of this study depicted that teachers expressed that the most important resources for multisensory teaching were sensory-based material that children with intellectual disabilities could see, hear, touch, or move. Visual materials like flashcards, charts, LED screens, and real objects helped children understand ideas better. Sound materials, such as songs, rhymes, and auditory tools, helped children who learned through

listening. Tactile-based materials, including blocks, beads, playdough, textured objects, sensory bins, and 3D models, helped or assisted children learn by feeling, touching, and doing. Teachers also said digital tools, like tablets, LEDs, educational apps, and multimedia devices, are helpful to make lessons more enjoyable, interesting, and interactive. Spaces for movement or sensory rooms are important for children who learn by moving.

4. Discussion

Multisensory teaching uses different senses like sight, hearing, touch, and movement, and helps children with intellectual disabilities learn. The study showed that teachers widely believe this approach is effective for teaching these children. Teachers explained that when children use several senses together, such as seeing, listening, touching, and moving, they can understand concepts more clearly. In classrooms, teachers regularly use real objects, pictures, flashcards, sensory boards, textures, and hands-on materials to show and teach concepts in a way children can experience and remember. Modification of modules, varied curricula, talent development, and one-teacher-one-student individual mentorship are examples of customized learning methodologies (Ariyani et al., 2025). It was found that multisensory teaching contributed to the development of essential skills on the far side of academics. In cases where a child needs more support, teachers even rely on one-to-one mentoring to make learning more personalized. Although they face practical challenges such as limited space, a shortage of materials, and wide differences in students' abilities. Teachers reported that these combined strategies led to visible improvements in children's independence and classroom participation. Despite these challenges, teachers unanimously agreed on multisensory teaching. Implementing significant policies, allocating required resources, and taking a comprehensive approach to address systemic barriers are all important to ensure fair learning opportunities (Muhammad Rafiq et al., 2025). Teachers didn't see multisensory teaching as something extra or optional. For them, it was an obligatory part of teaching children with intellectual disabilities. The findings revealed that using multisensory strategies constantly is important because these children learn in alternative ways. A combination of visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic activities is used by teachers because children with intellectual disabilities gain an understanding best when their senses are involved. It was very noticeable that the children did not respond equally to every activity; instead, they reacted more when the activity matched their personal interest or like better learning style. Video instruction takes a personalized, visual approach and requires teacher preparation and content creation; it can be used in special education programs (Ali et al., 2025). When video modeling is done by the teachers, videos keep children engaged, help them understand more, and allow them to practice new skills at their own pace. Although there has been interest in its use in audiovisual situations like podcasts and multilingual radio news (Pujadas-Farreras, 2025; Lisnawati et al., 2024). Teachers expressed that when children were permitted to move, jump, dance, or do small physical tasks, they remained focused for a longer time and understood instructions better. This suggests that physical engagement is not just a way to release energy; it actually supports learning for children with intellectual disabilities. Examining how exercise training programs affect the motor skills of individuals with intellectual disabilities (Zarei et al., 2024). Overall, the findings highlighted that no single method worked for every child. Teachers keep a close eye on each child and change activities depending on what helps them learn best. Multisensory teaching isn't just

an extra tool; it's something that is really needed when teaching children with intellectual disabilities. Researchers and practitioners have effectively employed assistive technology (AT) to improve task completion and independence for people with intellectual and developmental disabilities in both home and work situations (Randall et al., 2025). According to the study, special education (SE) teachers should be aware of their specific areas of specialty and consistently work hard to increase their professional experience and teaching proficiency (Arjumandi et al., 2024). One of their biggest challenge was the lack of resources and materials for intellectual disabilities. Although the quality of education was positively connected with teacher effectiveness, the limited correlation between resource availability and developmental outcomes required more strategic utilization of available resources (Dela Cerna et al., 2025). Another major challenge was the larger number of students in each class with intellectual disabilities. Since every child has different abilities, sensory preferences, and learning styles, it becomes more challenging for teachers to give individualized attention to every child. Furthermore, it is advantageous for them to be assigned unique duties that are tailored to their needs and offer them chances to succeed (Porter, 2022). Teachers also mentioned that their own training was limited. Despite such a challenge, they remained committed to using multisensory strategies because they noticed that the children learned better and stayed more engaged and focused when these methods were applied to the children with Intellectual disabilities. The current study contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the effects of trauma-informed training on educators who work with adolescents who have experienced trauma and intellectual disabilities (O'Connell & Berger, 2025).

Teachers used a wide range of strategies to make multisensory teaching suitable for every child, and their decisions were based mainly on constant observation. Multisensory approaches are a methodology based on teaching by combining sight, hearing, movement, and sensory intuition. Through multisensory techniques, it will be possible to learn new vocabulary and grammar not only by listening or reading, but also by seeing, writing, expressing, and sensory experience. As a result, more sensory organs participate in the learning process, strengthening and preserving knowledge in long-term memory (Dusboyeva, 2025). Teachers shared that they could not rely on a fixed method because each child responded differently to sensory input. By observing them closely, teachers learned the type of learning styles of their students with intellectual disabilities. This careful observation helped them adapt their teaching style in a way that matched the child's strengths and needs. Teachers need more institutional assistance and training. Teachers who identified as impaired had more skill and confidence when it comes to providing modifications and adaptations for children with intellectual disabilities (Smith & Myers, 2025). Overall, the findings show that teachers continuously change, modify, and reshape their teaching methods for children with intellectual disabilities to make learning enjoyable and accessible for every child. Their strategies are flexible rather than fixed, and their main goal is to ensure that each child gets the type of sensory input that helps them learn best. To develop artistic abilities, such as selecting the best educational strategies to employ and effectively integrating instructional and technical resources, the teacher has a significant role (Matallana & Paredes-Velasco, 2025).

Teachers can improve their learning objectives by using mobile phones as learning tools (Gul et al., 2021). Additionally, visual resources, such as flashcards, posters, LED screens, real-life objects, and simple pictures, play a crucial role in helping children with

intellectual disabilities understand what is being taught. Many children can remember information more easily when the teacher uses something they can actually watch, instead of only explaining verbally. It was found in this study that there is an importance of the sound-based or auditory-based materials for children with intellectual disabilities. Songs, music, poems, rhymes, clapping patterns, recorded instructions, and other auditory tools help children in learning and gaining understanding through listening. Another strong point raised by teachers was about tactile or hands-on resources. Materials like blocks, beads, textured items, playdough, sand trays, sensory bins, wooden shapes, and 3D models help children with intellectual disabilities who learn through touching and doing the material with their hands. The health of the handicapped community is seriously threatened by the low levels of exercise engagement (Jamieson et al., 2025).

5. Conclusion

The multisensory teaching approach is fundamentally very effective and essential for children with intellectual disabilities. The study concluded that teachers consider the multisensory teaching approach a mandatory and extremely valuable method for these children. The general opinion is that children achieve better comprehension, memory, and attention when learning is facilitated through visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic activities that help the children learn.

Despite many challenges, teachers successfully employ individualized adaptation as their primary strategy. Teachers have shown a deep reliance on close, continuous observation of their students' sensory preferences and learning styles. The strategies implemented include making tasks easier, dividing instructions into small parts, and adjusting the classroom setup. Moreover, crucial resources are required for the transition from satisfactory to best multisensory delivery. Beyond the clear need for tangible sensory materials. Therefore, teachers' role is significant to use multi-sensory approach in their classes to make it more effective for children.

6. Recommendations

1. The Special Education Department, Punjab, should arrange regular training and workshops for teachers on the areas of new multisensory teaching approaches and class management skills.

2. School heads should be provided with necessary need based budget so that they can provide important resources to their teachers, like sensory tools, including flashcards, audio tools, and textured objects.

3. Special education department Punjab should provide teacher's assistant in the classrooms of children with intellectual disabilities to help teachers in handling children to focus on their sensory needs.

4. The Special Education Department, Punjab, should develop a sensory guide book and a sensory book as per international standards and provide the same to the teachers so that they can apply multisensory teaching approaches in their classes.

5. Future researchers should explore the same phenomena with a different research design to get a different insight for bringing betterment in the lives of children with intellectual disabilities.

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